

DESIGN OF COMPOSITE LAMINATED STRUCTURES BY POLAR METHOD AND TOPOLOGY OPTIMISATION

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SUMMARY

In this paper, we propose a methodology for optimal design of composite plates undergoing in-plane or bending loads. The approach presented here is based on the use of the polar representation method for plane anisotropic tensors. The methodology is divided into two steps: in the first time, topology optimisation is performed in order to maximise the global rigidity of the structure in terms of the distributed elastic polar parameters in membrane or bending; further, an optimal stacking sequence with variable orientations throughout the plate is designed in order to match the optimal distribution of the plate polar parameters.

Keywords: Optimisation, Polar method, Laminates, Orthotropy, Elastic properties

THE PROBLEM OF DESIGNING THIN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Optimization is the process of designing structures that give the best response to a given set of criteria. Topology optimization also includes variational principles, in order to define the optimal distribution of matter, within a given domain and under given loads, with respect to a given criterion (i.e. maximising global stiffness).

Applied to composite materials, this methodology is twofold: it involves structural design — via topology optimization — as well as the definition of the local architecture of the material (i.e. fiber orientations), which is likely to change from one point of the structure to another, leading to variable stiffness laminates.

In this paper, we propose an approach to the optimisation of composite structures which is performed in two independent steps: first, the topological optimisation of the structure is performed and, in a second time, the optimal constitutive material is designed, which is a composite laminate with variable stacking sequence throughout the plate.

The first step of topological optimisation is performed using robust and convergent iterative algorithms [1]. Each iteration is composed of two steps of minimisation of the objective function, which is the complementary energy:

1. local minimisations of the complementary energy in terms of local elastic properties with a fixed state of stress;

2. global minimisation of the complementary energy in terms of stress components with fixed material properties.

One of the original features of the approach presented in this paper is the use of the polar method for the representation of plane anisotropic tensors. First of all, the polar method allows to completely develop the discussion of the minimisation of the complementary energy in an analytical way in the case of an orthotropic elastic material, thus giving exact results in terms of optimal polar parameters of the constitutive material. The polar method also allows to express the conditions on the appropriate shapes of orthotropy in order to be able to design optimal stacking sequences for laminates solutions. Additionally, the present approach allows to extend the topological optimisation of composite plates to the case of bending loads as well (for in-plane cases, see also [2]).

Finally, we also show that the approach based on the polar representation allows to uncouple the optimisation of the structure and the design of the optimal laminates. As a matter of fact, solutions issued from the structural optimisation are optimal fields of the homogenised polar parameters of the plate (either in membrane or in bending) and, in a second step, the optimal design problem is to search for stacking sequences responding to the optimal distribution of polar parameters throughout the plate. At this stage, further conditions on the respect of elastic symmetries (uncoupling, orthotropy, etc.) as well as feasibility and technological constraints.

In this paper, we show that possible solutions to this problem can be found within a particular class of laminates: quasi-trivial angle-ply and cross-ply laminates.

THE POLAR METHOD

A fourth order tensor showing the symmetries of plane elasticity (e.g. stiffness tensor Q or compliance tensor S) is represented by five polar invariants. We use the symbols T_0 , T_1 , R_0 , R_1 and $\Phi_0 - \Phi_1$ for the polar invariants of stiffness Q and t_0 , t_1 , r_0 , r_1 and $\varphi_0 - \varphi_1$ for the ones of compliance S . The relations between Cartesian components and polar components for the stiffness tensor Q read:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q_{11} &= T_0 + 2T_1 + R_0 \cos 4\Phi_0 + 4R_1 \cos 2\Phi_1 \\
 Q_{12} &= -T_0 + 2T_1 - R_0 \cos 4\Phi_0 \\
 Q_{16} &= R_0 \sin 4\Phi_0 + 2R_1 \sin 2\Phi_1 \\
 Q_{22} &= T_0 + 2T_1 + R_0 \cos 4\Phi_0 - 4R_1 \cos 2\Phi_1 \\
 Q_{26} &= -R_0 \sin 4\Phi_0 + 2R_1 \sin 2\Phi_1 \\
 Q_{66} &= T_0 - R_0 \cos 4\Phi_0
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Similar relations can be written for the components of the compliance tensor S .

CLASSICAL LAMINATED PLATE THEORY

A composite laminated plate is stack of several elementary layers. Each layer is characterised by its position z through the thickness of the plate, its orientation $\delta(z)$, its thickness $h(z)$ and its elastic properties $Q(z)$.

The homogenisation rules give the elastic properties of an homogeneous material equivalent to either the in-plane or bending behaviour of the laminate in the frame of the Kirchhoff plate theory. In-plane and bending stiffness, A and D , are expressed as functions of the elastic properties $Q(z)$, the thickness $h(z)$ and the orientation $\delta(z)$ of the elementary layers:

$$A = \int_{-\frac{H}{2}}^{\frac{H}{2}} Q(z) dz \quad ; \quad D = \int_{-\frac{H}{2}}^{\frac{H}{2}} z^2 Q(z) dz \quad (2)$$

being H the total thickness of the plate. Tensors A and D can be normalised with respect to the total thickness H :

$$A^* = \frac{1}{H} A \quad ; \quad D^* = \frac{12}{H^3} D \quad (3)$$

We also introduce symbols a and d for the in-plane and bending compliance behaviours of the laminate, respectively.

Polar parameters of a laminate

By applying polar expressions (1) for the representation of tensor $Q(z)$ in equations (2), we get the polar parameters of the laminate for in-plane and bending stiffness (symbols $\bar{\bullet}$ and $\tilde{\bullet}$ respectively):

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \bar{T}_0 = \int_{-\frac{H}{2}}^{\frac{H}{2}} T_0(z) dz \\ \bar{T}_1 = \int_{-\frac{H}{2}}^{\frac{H}{2}} T_1(z) dz \\ \bar{R}_0 e^{4i\phi_0} = \int_{-\frac{H}{2}}^{\frac{H}{2}} R_0(z) e^{4i(\phi_0(z)+\delta(z))} dz \\ \bar{R}_1 e^{2i\phi_1} = \int_{-\frac{H}{2}}^{\frac{H}{2}} R_1(z) e^{2i(\phi_1(z)+\delta(z))} dz \end{array} \right. \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{T}_0 = \int_{-\frac{H}{2}}^{\frac{H}{2}} z^2 T_0(z) dz \\ \tilde{T}_1 = \int_{-\frac{H}{2}}^{\frac{H}{2}} z^2 T_1(z) dz \\ \tilde{R}_0 e^{4i\phi_0} = \int_{-\frac{H}{2}}^{\frac{H}{2}} z^2 R_0(z) e^{4i(\phi_0(z)+\delta(z))} dz \\ \tilde{R}_1 e^{2i\phi_1} = \int_{-\frac{H}{2}}^{\frac{H}{2}} z^2 R_1(z) e^{2i(\phi_1(z)+\delta(z))} dz \end{array} \right. \quad (4)$$

THE PROBLEM OF STRUCTURAL OPTIMISATION

Optimisation criterion

The objective of the structural optimisation is the maximisation of the global stiffness of a linear elastic structure. This is possible through the minimisation of the global compliance G , which is the work of exterior forces applied onto the structure and is equal to the double of the elastic energy in the case of a linear elastic structure:

$$G = \int_S a S_{ijkl} \sigma_{ij} \sigma_{kl} dS \quad (5)$$

Under the hypothesis of fixed null displacements of the frontier of the domain S , the theorem of complementary energy implies:

$$G = \min_{\tau \in \Sigma_{ad}} \left(\int_S a S_{ijkl} \tau_{ij} \tau_{kl} dS \right)$$

Stress components $\sigma_{\alpha\beta}$, the parameter α and the homogenised compliance tensor S in formulas (5) and (6) are defined as:

- for in-plane loads: $\sigma_{\alpha\beta} = N_{\alpha\beta}$ are the in-plane efforts, $S = a^*$ and $\alpha = 1/H$;
- for bending loads: $\sigma_{\alpha\beta} = M_{\alpha\beta}$ are the bending moments, $S = d^*$ and $\alpha = 12/H^3$.

Optimisation parameters

For sake of simplicity, we note $t_0, t_1, r_0, r_1, \varphi_0$ and φ_1 the polar parameters of the compliance tensor S , $T_0, T_1, R_0, R_1, \Phi_0$ and Φ_1 the ones of the stiffness tensor $Q = S^{-1}$.

The elastic tensors are orthotropic, and that implies:

$$\varphi_0 - \varphi_1 = k \frac{\pi}{4} \quad \text{and} \quad \Phi_0 - \Phi_1 = K \frac{\pi}{4} \quad (6)$$

being k and K are characteristic parameters for the shapes of orthotropy for compliance and for stiffness, respectively ($k = 0$ or 1 , and $K = 0$ or 1). Additionally, we consider the most general case of laminates made of identical layers, and in this case the homogenised isotropic stiffness polar parameters of the laminate are the same as the ones of the elementary layer:

$$T_0 = T_0^{\text{EL}} \quad \text{and} \quad T_1 = T_1^{\text{EL}} \quad (7)$$

being $T_0^{\text{EL}}, T_1^{\text{EL}}, R_0^{\text{EL}}, R_1^{\text{EL}}$ the stiffness polar parameters of the elementary layer.

Therefore, the optimisation parameters are the anisotropic polar components R_0 and R_1 , and the principal direction of orthotropy Φ_1 .

Optimisation constraints

The constraints of the optimisation problem are defined by the limit values for the optimisation parameters (box constraints) and by the thermodynamic conditions of existence for the stiffness elastic tensor:

$$\begin{cases} R_0 \in [0, R_0^{\text{EL}}] \\ R_1 \in [0, R_1^{\text{EL}}] \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{cases} T_0^{\text{EL}} - R_0 > 0 \\ T_1^{\text{EL}} (T_0^{\text{EL}} + R_0) - 2R_1^2 > 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Formulation of the optimisation problem

The structural optimisation problem is in the form of a double minimisation with respect to the material elastic parameters (R_0, R_1, Φ_1) and with respect to the stress tensor τ [1]:

$$\min G = \min_{(R_0, R_1, \Phi_1)} \left[\min_{\tau \in \Sigma_{ad}} \left(\int_S a S_{ijkl} \tau_{ij} \tau_{kl} dS \right) \right] \quad (9)$$

under the conditions of constraints expressed by (8).

THE OPTIMISATION ALGORITHM

The optimisation problem is solved using an optimisation iterative algorithm divided into two steps:

- **Initialisation:** definition of the mesh, boundary conditions, initial values of the optimisation variables, first finite element calculation of the stress throughout the structure.
- **Iteration:** each iteration is itself divided into two steps, a local minimisation with fixed state of stress and a global minimisation with fixed material parameters (F.E. calculation of the stresses).

Convergence of the algorithm is proved on the basis of the properties of the local minimisation and the theorem of the complementary energy.

Local minimisation

The optimal orientation for the principal axes of orthotropy Φ_1^{opt} corresponds to the direction associated to the principal stress which is the greater in absolute value:

$$\Phi_1^{\text{opt}} = \text{direction} \left[\max(|\sigma_I|, |\sigma_{II}|) \right] \quad (10)$$

In each point of the structure, the stress tensor is described by the polar components T and R , and particularly it is characterised by the stress parameter X : $X = R/|T|$.

The minimisation of the complementary energy with respect to the material elastic parameters is performed for a fixed value of X , and the optimal polar parameters depend on X ($X \in [0, +\infty[$). The analytical discussion of the minimisation leads to the following results for various ranges of variation of the stress parameter X :

- **Case 1** (free stacking sequence): if $0 \leq X \leq \sqrt{\frac{T_0^{\text{EL}}}{2T_1^{\text{EL}}}}$, optimal solutions are:
 - $K = 0$ and $R_1^{\text{opt}} = XT_1^{\text{EL}}$ and $0 \leq R_0^{\text{opt}} \leq R_0^{\text{EL}}$;
 - $K = 1$ and $R_1^{\text{opt}} = XT_1^{\text{EL}}$ and $0 \leq R_0^{\text{opt}} \leq T_0^{\text{EL}} - 2T_1^{\text{EL}}X^2$
- **Case 2** (free stacking sequence): if $\sqrt{\frac{T_0^{\text{EL}}}{2T_1^{\text{EL}}}} < X \leq \frac{R_1^{\text{EL}}}{T_1^{\text{EL}}}$, optimal solutions are:
 - $K = 0$ and $R_1^{\text{opt}} = XT_1^{\text{EL}}$ and $0 \leq R_0^{\text{opt}} \leq 2T_1^{\text{EL}}X^2 - T_0^{\text{EL}}$;
 - $K = 1$: no solution
- **Case 3** (unidirectional laminate): if $\frac{R_1^{\text{EL}}}{T_1^{\text{EL}}} < X \leq \frac{T_0^{\text{EL}} + R_0^{\text{EL}}}{2R_1^{\text{EL}}}$, optimal solutions are:
 - $K = 0$ and $R_0^{\text{opt}} = R_0^{\text{EL}}$ and $R_1^{\text{opt}} = R_1^{\text{EL}}$

– **Case 4** (cross-ply laminate): if $\frac{T_0^{\text{EL}} + R_0^{\text{EL}}}{2R_1^{\text{EL}}} < X < +\infty$, optimal solutions are:

$$\circ \quad K = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad R_0^{\text{opt}} = R_0^{\text{EL}} \quad \text{and} \quad R_1^{\text{opt}} = \frac{T_0^{\text{EL}} + R_0^{\text{EL}}}{2X}$$

DESIGN OF THE OPTIMAL STACKING SEQUENCE

Given the distribution of the optimal homogenised polar parameters of the laminate throughout the structure, which is issued from the structural optimisation algorithm, the design of the optimal laminate is performed. That corresponds to the search of a stacking sequence with variable orientations within each layer and throughout the structure which matches the optimal distribution of polar parameters. Additionally, constraints must be imposed on the respect of continuity of fibres within each layer and on elastic symmetries (uncoupling, in-plane or bending orthotropy).

The optimal solution is represented by the set of constitutive parameters of the laminate (number of layers, material and thickness of the elementary layer, orientation angles and stacking sequence) which can be directly used in order to build up the laminate.

Formulation of the design problem for the optimal laminates

Let us consider a plate under an in-plane load (or a bending load). The step of the topological optimisation of the structure, which is described in the previous section, gives the optimal polar elastic moduli of in-plane stiffness \bar{R}_0^{opt} , \bar{R}_1^{opt} as well as the optimal in-plane orthotropy direction $\bar{\Phi}_1^{\text{opt}}$ in each point of the structure, that is to say in each element of the mesh (the same results apply to the case of a bending load, the optimal polar moduli and angle being \tilde{R}_0^{opt} , \tilde{R}_1^{opt} and $\tilde{\Phi}_1^{\text{opt}}$).

The chosen structure of the material for the local minimisation is a laminate made of n identical UD layers (see equations (7) and (8)), which is locally uncoupled and orthotropic in membrane (or bending). Therefore the optimal design problem of the stacking sequence reads:

Find an orthotropic uncoupled stacking sequence $[\delta_1(\bar{x}), \delta_2(\bar{x}), \dots, \delta_n(\bar{x})]^{\text{opt}}$

$$\text{such that:} \quad \begin{cases} \bar{R}_0([\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_n]^{\text{opt}}) = \bar{R}_0^{\text{opt}} \\ \bar{R}_1([\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_n]^{\text{opt}}) = \bar{R}_1^{\text{opt}} \\ \bar{\Phi}_1([\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_n]^{\text{opt}}) = \bar{\Phi}_1^{\text{opt}} \end{cases}$$

being $\delta_k^{\text{opt}}(\bar{x})$ ($k = 1, 2, \dots, n$) the optimal orientation at point \bar{x} within the k^{th} layer of the laminate. The same formulation of the optimal design problem applies for the case of bending properties. No preliminary hypothesis is made on the stacking sequence, thus the formulation is completely general.

Resolution of the optimal design problem using angle-ply and cross-ply laminates

In this paper, we show that a solution to the optimisation problem for the stacking sequence can be found analytically for every case of optimal elastic moduli R_0^{opt} , R_1^{opt} (see section “Local minimisation”) by using particular classes of stacking sequences: cross-ply and balanced angle-ply laminates.

For these laminates the expression of the polar moduli R_0 and R_1 are simple and depend only on a single parameter of the stack:

- angle $\pm\alpha$ for an angle-ply,
- ratio h between thickness of the 0° -layer and the global thickness for a cross-ply.

Particularly, we have:

$$\alpha^{\text{opt}} = \frac{1}{2} \arccos\left(\frac{\bar{R}_1^{\text{opt}}}{\bar{R}_1^{\text{EL}}}\right) \text{ for the angle-ply and } h^{\text{opt}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{\bar{R}_1^{\text{opt}}}{\bar{R}_1^{\text{EL}}}\right) \text{ for the cross-ply.}$$

It is important to remark that the optimal angle-ply and cross-ply stacking sequences are orthotropic for in-plane behaviour. Uncoupling can be achieved by the choice of quasi-trivial uncoupled solutions (see [3]), which are not necessarily symmetric.

The same results can be valid for the bending behaviour if the angle-ply or cross-ply stacking sequences are selected among the group of quasi-trivial quasi-homogeneous solutions [3].

EXAMPLES OF OPTIMISATION OF PLATES BY THE POLAR METHOD

The optimisation procedure makes use of the finite element code OpenFEM running in the MATLAB environment. We show here two numerical examples:

- a centre-hole plate under bi-axial in-plane loading;
- a rectangular plate under eccentric bending loading.

In both cases, we use a T300/5208 unidirectional carbone-epoxyde elementary layer: its polar components are given in Table 1.

Table1. Polar elastic properties of the UD carbone-epoxyde elementary layer.

$E_0^{\text{EL}} = 26.88 \text{ GPa}$			
$T_0^{\text{EL}} = 26.88 \text{ GPa}$	$T_1^{\text{EL}} = 24.74 \text{ GPa}$	$R_0^{\text{EL}} = 19.71 \text{ GPa}$	$R_1^{\text{EL}} = 21.43 \text{ GPa}$

For each case we will show the optimal distribution of polar parameters and the corresponding angle-ply or cross-ply optimal stacking sequences.

Center-hole plate under bi-axial loading

The structure and its boundary conditions are shown in Figure 1: in-plane loads are applied on the sides of the plate, being $F_x = 20$ kN/m and $F_y = 10$ kN/m.

Figure 1. Center-hole plate under bi-axial loading.

The polar parameters for the initialisation are chosen as the ones of a unidirectional stacking sequence, i.e. $\bar{R}_0 = R_0^{EL}$, $\bar{R}_1 = R_1^{EL}$ and $\bar{\Phi}_1 = 0$ throughout the plate. The results of the structural optimisation $\bar{\Phi}_1^{opt}$, \bar{R}_0^{opt} and \bar{R}_1^{opt} are shown in Figure 2: with respect to the initial state of the structure, they correspond to a decrease of 65% in terms of global compliance and a decrease of 80% in terms of maximum displacement.

The result of the optimal design of the stacking sequence are shown in Figure 3: optimal distribution of angles $\delta_1^{opt} = \Phi_1^{opt} - \alpha^{opt}$ (being $\delta_2^{opt} = \Phi_1^{opt} + \alpha$) for the angle-ply solution.

Figure 2. Distribution of the optimal orientation $\bar{\Phi}_1^{opt}$ and polar moduli \bar{R}_0^{opt} and \bar{R}_1^{opt} .

Figure 3. Distribution of the optimal layer orientation $\delta_1^{\text{opt}} = \Phi_1^{\text{opt}} - \alpha^{\text{opt}}$ for an angle-ply

Rectangular plate in bending

The structure and its boundary conditions are shown in Figure 4: a surface force is applied on each load region of density $F_s = \pm 13 \text{ N/m}^2$.

The polar parameters for the initialisation are chosen as the ones of an isotropic stacking sequence, i.e. $\tilde{R}_0 = 0$, $\tilde{R}_1 = 0$ and $\tilde{\Phi}_1 = 0$ throughout the plate. The results of the structural optimisation $\tilde{\Phi}_1^{\text{opt}}$, \tilde{R}_0^{opt} and \tilde{R}_1^{opt} are shown in Figures 5: with respect to the initial state of the structure, they correspond to a decrease of 57% in terms of global compliance and a decrease of 58% in terms of maximum displacement.

The result of the optimal design of the stacking sequence are shown in Figure 6: optimal distribution of the ratio of thicknesses h for a cross-ply laminate with plies oriented at Φ_1^{opt} and $\Phi_1^{\text{opt}} + \frac{\pi}{2}$.

Figure 4. Plate in bending: geometry and loads.

Figure 5. Distribution of the optimal orientation $\tilde{\Phi}_1^{\text{opt}}$ and polar moduli \tilde{R}_0^{opt} and \tilde{R}_1^{opt} .

Figure 6. Distribution of the optimal ratio of thicknesses h^{opt} for a cross-ply laminate.

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